

2023 UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) and University of Surrey Open and Transparent Research Practices Survey

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Executive Summary

The 2023 UKRN Open and Transparent Research Practices (OTRP) Survey was created as a component of the UKRN Open Research Programme and ran across 15 universities¹ affiliated with the programme at the start of 2023. At Surrey, we expanded the scope of the survey questions to gather data relevant to our strategic priorities and to facilitate tracking of progress against the baseline of our 2020 Open Research Practices survey. The goals of the survey were to help identify training gaps, to monitor Open Research awareness, attitudes, and behaviours, and to understand the barriers and opportunities in implementing Open Research practices that researchers may experience. Through the survey we hoped to gain insight into what can be done to further facilitate and support Open Research at the University of Surrey.

The survey ran at the University of Surrey from 23rd January – 31st March 2023, and was open to all research active staff and PGRs across all disciplines. The survey covered 14 Open Research topics and was designed to take 20-30 minutes to complete. Due to a low completion rate of the full UKRN survey, we kept the Surrey-only questions open for a further 3 weeks, closing the condensed 5-minute version on 21st April 2023. Participation was anonymous and incentivised via a prize draw to win one of ten £50 Amazon vouchers (supplied by the UKRN).

The analysis reported here is based on the combined responses to the UKRN questions and the Surrey-only extension (see Appendix G for all survey questions).

Sampling and interpretation

The sample self-selected to take part. Consequently, an individual's decision to take part in the survey may be causally related to their interest in Open Research, potentially leading to a response bias. Additionally, the opportunity to win £50 may have disproportionately attracted PGRs and ECRs. Nonetheless, the responses do cover participants from the range of Faculties (Q2) and career stages (Q4) within the University, and they reflect gender (Q5) and ethnicity (Q6) distributions similar to those found at the University. Therefore, in this regard, the sample captures the diversity of the University's researcher population.

Response rate

Across all 15 UKRN universities that ran the UKRN survey, 2,594 participants started the survey and 515 completed (20%)². At Surrey, the questionnaire was emailed to all academic staff (n =

¹ Bristol, Glasgow, KCL, Keele, Liverpool, Manchester, Newcastle, Northumbria, Oxford, Oxford Brookes, Reading, Sheffield, Southampton, Surrey, UCL.

² Information based on the UKRN reported values.

1,804) and PGRs (n = 1,306)³. A total of 214 participants started the UKRN survey (which represents 8% of all participants who started the UKRN survey), and 92 completed (43% completion rate). In our condensed 5-minute version of the survey, a further 150 participants started and 104 completed (69% completion rate).

In total, 364 Surrey participants responded to the survey (12% response rate). Note that this response rate is relatively low compared to the Surrey 2020 Survey (20% response rate), and likely due to the full UKRN survey being long, as well as general survey fatigue within the University population.

Main Findings

Surrey-only Questions

- Nine Open Research practices were presented: Open access, ORCID identifier, open data/sharing data, preprints, open software/code, open licences, open educational resources, study preregistration, and open monographs. There was a reasonably high level of awareness for most practices (ranging from 24.6% to 92.7%) (Q7). The exceptions were open educational resources (39.5%), study preregistration (38.2%), and open monographs (24.6%). These practices are less broadly applicable across disciplines than the other practices listed.
- Respondents indicated that support-related factors were the greatest barriers to the uptake of Open Research in their field: Lack of funding (23.6%), lack of time (22.7%), and lack of positive incentives (12.8%) were the most frequently cited barriers (Q8).
- When thinking about their careers (Q9), respondents considered Open Access (76.3%), ORCID (72.6%), and open data (63.6%) most important, with preregistration (30.1%), monographs (29.6%), and preprints (24.6%) being considered the least.
- About half of the respondents were either already applying for funding to support data sharing (25.9%) or planned to (21.3%), with 28.7% not knowing whether it is possible with their funders (Q11).
- Most respondents (86.5%) indicated that they work with data, while 8% did not (Q10). However, responses to Q12, that asks indirectly about data usage, imply that the 8% who claimed not to work with data may indeed be involved with data-related work. This discrepancy, that Q10 and Q12 aimed to investigate, suggests a potential misunderstanding of the term 'data' among 8% of respondents.
- The most frequent concerns about open data/data sharing (Q13) were: the data contain sensitive and/or personal information (44%), organising data in a presentable and useful way (26.2%), not knowing what repository to use (21.5%), and unsure about copyright and licensing (21.5%). The least frequent concerns were data are too small or unimportant (3.7%), I have no desire to share my data (3.1%), others may not be able to repeat my findings (3.1%).
- The most frequent incentives to open data/data sharing (Q14) were public benefit (50.8%), increased impact and visibility of my research (47.6%), and transparency (37.2%). The least frequent incentives were: I don't perceive any incentives to sharing my data (7.3%), my data can be used in teaching (4.7%), and my data will have a DOI (3.1%).

³ Figures based on the [KPI dashboard](#) (accessed on 20.09.23): Headcount of academic staff on 28th Feb 2023 (based on the staff population summary and then selecting all faculties using the "division" filter), and PGR students for 2022/2023.

- A large percentage of respondents (78.1%) reported using internal University of Surrey sources as either their primary (45.7%) or supplementary (32.4%) reference for information, training, and guidance on Open Research practices, with just 21.8% mainly relying on non-Surrey sources (Q15). The most frequently mentioned specific sources of information were the Open Research webpages (40.0%), training module (31.8%), and supervisor, line manager or Surrey peer or colleague (27.2%) (Q16).
- The majority of respondents (72.3%) had the autonomy to make decisions about where to publish their research (Q17). When selecting a journal, respondents ranked the journal aims and scope make it a good fit for my topic, journal impact factor (JIF), and research rigour as the three primary factors they took into account (Q18).
- When asked about responsible metrics, 41.5% of respondents reported being unfamiliar with the term. Around a quarter (23%) felt that such metrics were relevant, and generally practised responsibly, and 20% that they were relevant but not always practised responsibly (Q19).
- Around half the respondents (46.7%) were clear or very clear about what Open Research practices they should be engaging in to meet University policy, 27.2% were unclear or very unclear, and 26.2% were neither clear nor unclear (Q20).
- Respondents were asked whether they thought that the Open Research culture at the University had changed over the past three years (Q21). Around half (46.2%) felt that the culture had improved, 5% felt the culture had not changed, and 2% felt that there was less of an Open Research culture. The remaining respondents did not know (23.6%) or had not been at the University for three years (22.6%).
- In response to a qualitative question asking what one thing the University could do to promote an Open Research culture, respondents suggested providing clear, concise communication about which practices are necessary, increasing funding, providing more time, recognition and rewards, and resources and training. They also suggested that support at Faculty level would be useful. Notably, a number of suggestions were for support mechanisms that are already in place. For example, the Open Research Champions, Open Research checklist and Open Research training module (Q22).
- Responses to the 'comments' question were predominantly idiosyncratic. The themes that emerged related to Open Research taking time and effort, the survey being too long, and funding required to support Open Access (Q23).

UKRN Questions

- Fourteen Open Research practices were presented: Research co-production, conducting Open Research consistent with relevant legal, ethical, and regulatory constraints, transparent qualitative data practices, defining the data, code, or other evidence (e.g., data management plans), preregistration, open source software created by others, creating own open source software/analysis code, version control, own data analysis computationally reproducible, preparing according to FAIR principles, guidelines for recognising contributions, declaring conflicts of interest, preprints, and Open Access publications. In response to questions Q1.1 to Q14.1, regarding whether each of the 14 open practices were a priority in the researchers' field of research, the three practices most frequently designated as 'high' priority were: Open Access (78.3%), conducting Open Research consistent with relevant legal, ethical, and regulatory constraints (69.9%), and declaring conflicts of interest (67.4%). The three practices least frequently considered high priority were: Preprints (28.3%), and preregistration (28.2%), and creating open source software (16.5%) (see Appendix E).

- On average, 17% of respondents had looked for training and support for Open Research practices at their institution (range: 4.3% - 45.5%; (Questions Q1.4 to Q14.4). Of those that had looked for help, 51.9% described the help as 'good' (range: 28.6% - 76.2%) and 35.9% as the right level (range: 23.5% - 50%)(Questions Q1.7 to Q14.7). Note that questions Q1.7 to Q14.7 were only answered by a small subset of the sample ($M = 19.7$, range: 4 - 64), and that answers were a list of descriptive options, not a scale.

How have researchers' awareness, attitudes, and behaviours regarding Open Research evolved from the 2020 baseline survey to the 2023 follow-up survey?

The inaugural [University of Surrey Questionnaire on Open Research Practices](#) ran from February to May 2020. The survey was emailed to all academic staff and PGRs at the University. It was designed to take approximately 15 minutes to complete. A response rate of 20% ($N=537$) was achieved. Unlike the 2023 survey, the 2020 version included only Surrey questions. Except where noted, questions were asked like-for-like in both the 2020 and 2023 surveys. Here we use the 2020 survey as a baseline against which to assess changes at the University over the last three years.

Awareness (Q7): In the 2023 survey, awareness of broadly applicable practices, such as Open Access, ORCID identifier, and open data/data sharing, continues to remain high at over 70% of respondents. However, there is a slight decline (-5.2%) in awareness across most practices; only awareness of ORCID (+2.7%) and preprints (+7.8%) has increased compared to 2020. This reduction may be attributed to a higher percentage of junior and early-career researchers participating in the 2023 survey. However, the 2020 survey did not capture data regarding career stage for all respondents, so this theory cannot be definitively confirmed. The question format also differed between the two surveys.

Practice (UKRN Q1.2 to 14.2): We were not able to compare the percentage of respondents using Open Research practices across the two surveys for several reasons: Both the question wording and the answer format differed between the 2020 Surrey and the 2023 UKRN questions. The various practices were also described using different terminology. For example, the 2020 survey asked about the practice of 'open software/code', whereas the 2023 survey asked separately about 'using open source software created by others' and 'creating my own open source software/analysis code to share with others'. There was also an inconsistency within the survey between responses to the Surrey question about awareness (Q7), and UKRN questions related to awareness (Q1.1 - 14. 1) and practice (Q1.2 - 14.2) of various Open Research practices (see Appendix A).

Open Research barriers (Q8): Overall, a consistent pattern of barriers was observed across both surveys. Comparing the top three most frequently mentioned barriers, lack of funding (23.6%) remains the most frequently cited obstacle. In 2023, lack of time (22.7%) has moved into the second position, with more respondents identifying it as a concern compared to 2020 (13.2%). Lack of information, which held the third spot in the 2020 survey, has now dropped to the sixth position in 2023, being replaced by lack of incentives (12.8%). Notably, since the 2020 survey, significant efforts have been invested in enhancing access to Open Research information at the University. The decline in the ranking of lack of information, from 16.4% to 6.4% in 2023, suggests that researchers have made use of these resources.

Importance for career development (Q9): In the 2023 survey, respondents consistently rated all open practices as more 'important' or 'very important' for their career ($M = 61.9%$) compared to the 2020 survey ($M = 39.6%$). ORCID (+25.7%), preregistration (+30.9%), and open monographs (+31.2%), saw the most significant increase in ratings when compared to 2020, with perceived importance more than doubling for the latter two practices.

Problems or concerns with sharing data (Q13): Across both surveys, two persistent concerns featured in the top three: the presence of sensitive or personal information within the data and uncertainties regarding copyright and licensing. In 2023, organising data in a presentable and useful way, and I do not know what repository to use (jointly ranked third with copyright and licensing), were also ranked in the top three. In contrast, in 2020, unsure I have the rights to share, occupied the third position.

Incentives for data sharing (Q14): Across both surveys, two incentives remained consistently within the top three: Public benefit, and increased impact and visibility of my research. In 2023, transparency was also ranked among the top three incentives. In contrast, in 2020, increased opportunities for collaboration, occupied the third position. Note that in the 2020 survey, transparency and reuse were combined, but in the 2023 survey they were presented as separate options.

Information, training, and guidance (Q16): In the 2023 survey, the top three specific sources of information for researchers at Surrey were the Surrey Open Research webpages (40%), Surrey Open Research training module (31.8%), and supervisor, line manager or Surrey peer or colleague (27.2%). Notably, the Surrey Open Research webpages and the training module, which were introduced (module) and expanded (webpages) based on feedback from the 2020 survey, emerged as crucial resources for researchers. In 2020, researchers relied most on the literature (38.1%), non-Surrey peer or colleague/networking at conferences (37.6%), and common practice in the department or lab (26.3%).

Changes in Open Research culture (Q21): Among respondents who had been at the University for the past three years, almost two-thirds (60%) felt that the Open Research culture had improved. Approximately one-third did not know, 7% felt it had not changed, and just 3% felt that there was less of an Open Research culture.

Based on the findings from the Surrey-specific questions, the following actions are recommended:

- **Funding to support data sharing:** To address the fact that 29% of respondents are uncertain about the possibility of seeking support for data sharing from their funder (Q11), 1) Faculty Research and Innovation Officers (FRIOs) will communicate their new costing guidance as part of the soft launch of worktribe⁴. 2) Surrey Research Compute to socialise support and guidance on data management costs⁵ and integrate into Worktribe 3) FRIOs to work with the library and Surrey Research Compute to determine whether there are further Open Research related costs that need to be factored into the costing guidance.
- **Funding to support Open Access:** To address the barrier of lack of funding, particularly for Open Access publishing and monographs (Q22 & Q23) (noting existing awareness of the library Open Access fund): 1) Increase awareness of publisher agreements by updating our webpages and delivering additional sessions to the Faculties and Doctoral College. 2) Increase awareness of the different funders who supply funding for Open Access either as part of OA block grants or as part of grant awards (see *Focus on Communications*). 3)

⁴ This includes information on costings to consider related to data sharing including staff time associated with preparing data for sharing (e.g., data manager, technician, researcher), software, transcription and training costs, as well as data storage costs.

⁵ This includes information on costings to consider related to software, computational resources and Research Software Engineer requirements, as well as matched funding requests for computational infrastructure.

Provide information on different monograph publishers, and the options available via funders on our webpages.

- **Data sharing barriers:** To address the most frequent concerns about sharing data (Q13: 1. the data contain sensitive and/or personal information (44%); 2. organising data in a presentable and useful way (26.2%); 3. not knowing what repository to use (21.5%); 4. and unsure about copyright and licensing (21.5%)): 1) Highlight relevant webpages; 2) Highlight relevant training sessions/workshops on data sharing/data. 3) Highlight weekly Tuesday morning RDM drop-in sessions. 4) For international research, FRIOs to direct researchers to the Trusted Research and Data Management Strategy. 5) Surrey Research Compute to develop a new seamless data management ecosystem with a well-defined “Metadata Chain”: Data Stage/Data Bank/Data Finder.
- **Data sharing incentives:** To maximise awareness of the incentives respondents mentioned in relation to data sharing (Q14); 1) disseminate success stories, such as those illustrating public benefits or heightened impact (e.g. as case studies / news items; 2) Broaden communication of incentives related to REF2029 requirements; 3) Encourage senior colleagues with recognised track records in producing open data, to share examples.
- **Responsible metrics:** To increase awareness of the term responsible metrics (Q19): 1) Use communications to emphasise responsible use of metrics as an important part of research culture and point researchers to existing webpage; 2) Increase awareness of the sector Responsible Metrics frameworks and developments; 3) Consider inviting a speaker to present on responsible metrics for the 2025 Open Research / Research Culture Event; 4) Appoint two new Academic Leads in (a) Research Culture and (b) Research Governance and Integrity; 5) Review the RM Implementation Plan (2021) as part of forthcoming 5-year Research Culture strategy (strategy lead: Academic Lead for Research Culture).
- **Focus on Engagement across Research Life Cycle and Education:** The feedback received in response to Q8 indicates lack of time. This suggests that engaging Open Research Practices is not a priority (also see *Reward and Recognition*). To increase engagement: 1) surface information at the time of need in the research lifecycle. For example, embed relevant information on funding for data sharing / publications in bid development support (see *Funding to support Data Sharing*). 2) embed information on Open Research practices into education delivery by including information on OR in the Academics skills module delivered by the Library (with a related aim to increase the use of OA publications in academics’ teaching; see *Funding to support Open Access*); 3) link information on getting started with Open Research to the Postgraduate Researcher Progress Review Forms.
- **Focus on communications:** Notably, in response to the question (Q22), respondents requested resources already in existence. Responses to Q15 and Q16 further substantiate that researchers value University resources when they are aware of their availability. This underscores the need for: 1) comprehensive communication strategies across various channels, including School meetings, events, inductions, Champions, communications from the new PVCRI, and newsletters; 2) Open Research webpages being kept up to date (as is current practice).
- **Open Research policy:** The feedback received in response to Q20 and Q22 indicates that there is a lack of clarity within the University community regarding Surrey Open Research policies and the specific steps required for compliance. There is a need for; 1) coordinated effort to effectively communicate the availability of our open resources, with a particular focus on the Open Research Checklist, the role of Open Research Champions, and the training module; 2) as a result of the survey findings, copy that highlights the Open Research policies and the Open Research Checklist has been added to the [Getting Started](#) webpage.

- **Reward & Recognition:** To address the lack of reward and recognition for Open Research: 1) Continue Open Research awards scheme and Open Research badges for completing the Open Research module; 2) Include illustrative Open Research examples to support Criteria for Academic promotion; 3) Consider whether Open Research training could be recognised as part of the Post Graduate Certificate in Learning and Teaching in HE.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank all members of the University of Surrey who participated in this research and provided insights into their Open Research experiences. Thanks to you, we have a better understanding of the barriers and opportunities researchers experience in relation to Open Research, and this enables us to better support you.

Demographics

Q1: How would you describe the research methods you mainly use?

	n	%
Quantitative	124	40.3
Mixed	120	39.0
Qualitative	54	17.5
Other:	10	3.2
Total	308	100.0

n = 56 participants have not answered.

Other	n
Clinical	1
Conceptual and quantitative	1
Conceptual, mathematical and numerical	1
I am not in research	1
Not currently in research	1
Qualitative, Doctrinal (typical in law, concerned with applying legal rules), Analytical/Conceptual	1
Theoretical/philosophical	1

Exclusions

Data from two participants was excluded because they reported that they did not work in research. Therefore, the results reported below are based on the following data:

	n	%
UKRN	213	58.8
Surrey	149	41.2
Total	362	100.0

Q2: Please tell us which Faculty you are currently based in.

	n	%
FHMS	138	38.8
FEPS	126	35.4
FASS	78	21.9
Other (please specify)	11	3.1
Professional Services	3	0.8
Total	356	100.0

n = 6 participants have not answered.

Other	n
Surrey Institute of Education	3
CVSSP	1
SHTM	1
university of surrey	1
Visiting PG/R	1

Q3: Please indicate your research discipline:

	n	%
(CAH10) Engineering and technology	49	16.0
(CAH15) Social sciences	37	12.1
(CAH02) Subjects allied to medicine (e.g., nursing, pharmacology, health sciences)	32	10.5
(CAH04) Psychology	32	10.5
(CAH05) Veterinary sciences	30	9.8
(CAH07) Physical sciences	29	9.5
(CAH03) Biological and sport sciences	22	7.2
(CAH17) Business and management	18	5.9
(CAH26) Geography, earth, and environmental studies	10	3.3
(CAH16) Law	9	2.9
(CAH19) Language and area studies	8	2.6
(CAH22) Education and teaching	7	2.3
(CAH25) Design, and creative and performing arts	7	2.3
(CAH06) Agriculture, food, and related studies	5	1.6
(CAH01) Medicine and dentistry	4	1.3
(CAH11) Computing	4	1.3
(CAH09) Mathematical sciences	3	1.0

	n	%
Total	306	100.0

n = 56 participants have not answered.

Q4: What is your career stage? [Please take a look at [here](#) if the choices below are not clear and choose the most appropriate.]

	n	%
Phase 1: Junior (e.g., PhD candidate, Research Assistant)	102	33.3
Phase 2: Early (e.g., Research Associate, first grant holder, Lecturer)	90	29.4
Phase 3: Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior Lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher)	68	22.2
Phase 4: Established/Experienced (e.g., Professor, Principal Fellows or Scientists)	46	15.0
Total	306	100.0

n = 56 participants have not answered.
For career stage by Faculty, see Appendix B.

Q5: What gender do you identify with?

	n	%
Woman	157	51.5
Man	135	44.3
Prefer to not disclose	9	3.0
Non-binary	4	1.3
Total	305	100.0

n = 57 participants have not answered.

Q6: What is your ethnic group?

	n	%
White	203	66.6
Asian or Asian-British	49	16.1
Other ethnic group	28	9.2
Black, Black-British, Caribbean or African	13	4.3
Mixed or multiple ethnic groups	12	3.9
Total	305	100.0

n = 57 participants have not answered.

Surrey Open Research Questions

Q7: Which of the following practices are you aware of? Hover over each item for more information (hovering only works on a computer). Please tick all that apply.

Respondents were asked about awareness of nine Open Research practices. Respondents were most frequently aware of Open Access (92.7%), ORCID identifier (81.1%), and open data/sharing data (72.4%). The practices that respondents reported being least aware of were open educational resources (39.5%), preregistration (38.2%), and open monographs (24.6%). This result is likely because these practices are less broadly applicable across disciplines, as shown by lower awareness of preregistration from FASS and FEPS, than FHMS, and higher awareness of open monographs from FASS than FHMS and FEPS. Just 4% of participants reported being unaware of any Open Research practices.

	n	% of respondents aware
Open access	279	92.7
ORCID identifier	244	81.1
Open data/sharing data	218	72.4
Preprints	198	65.8
Open software/code	188	62.5
Open licences	181	60.1
Open educational resources	119	39.5
Study preregistration	115	38.2
Open monographs	74	24.6
I'm not aware of any of these practices	12	4.0

n = 301 participants have answered.

n = 61 participants have not answered.

By faculty: There is some variation in awareness by faculty: Notably, across all practices other than monographs, awareness is higher in FHMS than FEPS and FASS.

	FHMS		FEPS		FASS	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Open access	124	96.1	80	87.9	66	91.7
ORCID identifier	112	86.8	69	75.8	57	79.2
Open data/sharing data	104	80.6	63	69.2	44	61.1
Preprints	96	74.4	59	64.8	42	58.3
Open software/code	84	65.1	59	64.8	41	56.9
Open licences	82	63.6	51	56.0	40	55.6
Study preregistration	76	58.9	35	38.5	32	44.4
Open educational resources	47	36.4	19	20.9	28	38.9

	FHMS		FEPS		FASS	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Open monographs	25	19.4	16	17.6	21	29.2
I'm not aware of any of these practices	3	2.3	7	7.7	2	2.8

2020 vs 2023: In the 2020 survey, participants were asked about awareness of eight Open Research practices (open educational resources was added to the 2023 survey). For each of the practices, participants were asked to tick 'aware of', 'practicing myself' and/or 'accessing'. This differs from the 2023 format where participants were asked to tick 'aware of' (Q2) because UKRN questions x.2 ask about practice. The difference in question format should be considered when comparing data from the two surveys.

Overall, there is a small reduction of awareness across most Open Research practices. Only awareness of ORCID and preprints show increases versus 2020.

	2020 %	2023 %	difference
Open access	95.1	92.7	-2.4
ORCID identifier	78.4	81.1	2.7
Open data/sharing data	83.5	72.4	-11.1
Preprints	58.0	65.8	7.8
Open software/code	70.6	62.5	-8.1
Open licences	66.9	60.1	-6.8
Open educational resources	NA	39.5	NA
Study preregistration	47.6	38.2	-9.4
Open monographs	39.0	24.6	-14.4
I'm not aware of any of these practices	NA	4.0	NA

By career stage: As seniority increases, there is an incremental increase in awareness across all open practices.

	Junior		Early		Mid		Established	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Open access	85	85.0	83	95.4	66	97.1	45	97.8
ORCID identifier	68	68.0	74	85.1	60	88.2	42	91.3
Open data/sharing data	56	56.0	70	80.5	57	83.8	38	82.6
Open software/code	50	50.0	61	70.1	52	76.5	35	76.1
Preprints	47	47.0	58	66.7	47	69.1	34	73.9
Open licences	46	46.0	55	63.2	46	67.6	33	71.7
Open educational resources	33	33.0	32	36.8	33	48.5	24	52.2
Study preregistration	29	29.0	29	33.3	32	47.1	22	47.8

	Junior		Early		Mid		Established	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Open monographs	23	23.0	12	13.8	17	25.0	22	47.8
I'm not aware of any of these practices	7	7.0	3	3.4	1	1.5	1	2.2

Q8: Which do you perceive to be the greatest barrier to the uptake of open research practices in your field?

Lack of funding (23.6%), lack of time (22.7%), and lack of positive incentives (12.8%) were the most frequently cited greatest barriers to Open Research practices. Lack of support from senior researchers (4.4%), lack of supporting infrastructure (4.4%), and lack of interest from junior researchers (1.5%) were the least frequently cited barriers.

	n	%
Lack of dedicated funding	48	23.6
Lack of time	46	22.7
Lack of positive incentives	26	12.8
I am unfamiliar with open research practices	15	7.4
Other. Please explain:	14	6.9
Lack of information or training	13	6.4
Lack of mandates from funders, institutions or regulators	10	4.9
The level of adoption of open research practices in my field is already sufficient	10	4.9
Lack of support from senior researchers (e.g., supervisors and principal investigators)	9	4.4
Lack of supporting infrastructure (e.g., sufficient storage for open data / publishing platform for open monographs)	9	4.4
Lack of interest from junior researchers	3	1.5
Total	203	100.0

n = 159 participants have not answered.

Other	n
-	1
Challenges of applying generic approaches to a niche field.	1
Data confidentiality and IP	1
Difficulty and wrong incentives in social sciences; lack of awareness by global north scholars working and publishing for each other in sufficiently funded institutions	1
IPs associated with collaborative research with industry	1
It's horrendously complex. It requires reading tomes of legalese about contracts between the university and OA publishers which rapidly change.	1

Other	n
Lack of support from my line manager and/or group head and/or others in the university obsessed with Micro\$oft.	1
Lack of time, dedicated funding, positive incentives	1
Many of the above, eg lack of modelling by others in the field, and string commercial incentives otherwise.	1
Open data may be prohibited by the ethical approval even when data are anonymised	1
Real support from University. The burden is once again dumped on the researchers	1
Risk of propagation of unsound research prior to due process completion.	1
Some people don't value it - this could come under either lack of incentives or information/training	1
The costs involved with open access are high, can't always fund it.	1

2020 vs 2023: In the 2020 survey, participants were asked the same question (Q6): Overall, there is a similar pattern across the two surveys. Comparing the top three most frequently cited barriers, lack of funding remains the most frequently cited barrier. In 2023 lack of time takes the second position, with a greater number of respondents indicating it as an issue compared to 2020. Lack of information was ranked third in the 2020 survey, but has dropped to sixth in 2023. In the 2023 survey, it is replaced by lack of incentives.

	2020	2023	difference
	%	%	
Lack of dedicated funding	19.7	23.6	3.9
Lack of time	13.2	22.7	9.5
Lack of positive incentives	13.0	12.8	-0.2
I am unfamiliar with open research practices	10.8	7.4	-3.4
Other. Please explain:	6.3	6.9	0.6
Lack of information or training	16.4	6.4	-10.0
Lack of mandates from funders, institutions or regulators	9.6	4.9	-4.7
The level of adoption of open research practices in my field is already sufficient	1.4	4.9	3.5
Lack of support from senior researchers (e.g., supervisors and principal investigators)	3.4	4.4	1.0
Lack of supporting infrastructure (e.g., sufficient storage for open data / publishing platform for open monographs)	6.0	4.4	-1.6
Lack of interest from junior researchers	0.2	1.5	1.3

Q9: How important do you believe the following practices are for your career development (i.e., promotion, job applications)?

Results for each open practice are presented individually, and then summarised below.

In terms of **Open Access**, 76.3% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 8.4 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 15.3 % being neutral.

Open Access	n	%
Very important	94	49.5
Important	51	26.8
Neutral	29	15.3
Unimportant	11	5.8
Very unimportant	5	2.6
Total	190	100.0

n = 172 participants have not answered.

In terms of **open data/data sharing**, 63.6% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 11.8 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 24.6 % being neutral.

Open data	n	%
Important	63	33.7
Very important	56	29.9
Neutral	46	24.6
Unimportant	17	9.1
Very unimportant	5	2.7
Total	187	100.0

n = 175 participants have not answered.

In terms of **open software/code**, 51.1% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 22.2 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 26.7 % being neutral.

Open code	n	%
Neutral	48	26.7
Very important	47	26.1
Important	45	25.0
Unimportant	24	13.3
Very unimportant	16	8.9
Total	180	100.0

n = 182 participants have not answered.

In terms of **preregistration**, 38.1% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 30.1 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 31.9 % being neutral.

Preregistration	n	%
Neutral	52	31.9
Important	35	21.5
Unimportant	29	17.8
Very important	27	16.6
Very unimportant	20	12.3
Total	163	100.0

n = 199 participants have not answered.

In terms of **preprints**, 42.1% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 24.6 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 33.3 % being neutral.

Preprints	n	%
Neutral	57	33.3
Important	50	29.2
Unimportant	27	15.8
Very important	22	12.9
Very unimportant	15	8.8
Total	171	100.0

n = 191 participants have not answered.

In terms of **monographs**, 33.6% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 29.6 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 36.9 % being neutral.

Monographs	n	%
Neutral	55	36.9
Important	28	18.8
Unimportant	22	14.8
Very important	22	14.8
Very unimportant	22	14.8
Total	149	100.0

n = 213 participants have not answered.

In terms of **open licenses**, 58.4% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 17.3 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 24.3 % being neutral.

Licenses	n	%
Important	52	30.1
Very important	49	28.3
Neutral	42	24.3
Unimportant	18	10.4
Very unimportant	12	6.9
Total	173	100.0

n = 189 participants have not answered.

In terms of **ORCID identifier**, 72.6% respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 9 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 18.4 % being neutral.

ORCID	n	%
Very important	74	41.3
Important	56	31.3
Neutral	33	18.4
Unimportant	10	5.6
Very unimportant	6	3.4
Total	179	100.0

n = 183 participants have not answered.

In terms of **open educational resources**, 62 % respondents thought that the practice was important or very important for their career, 13.8 % of respondents thought it was unimportant or very unimportant, with 24.1 % being neutral.

Open Educational Resources	n	%
Very important	66	37.9
Important	42	24.1
Neutral	42	24.1
Unimportant	13	7.5
Very unimportant	11	6.3
Total	174	100.0

n = 188 participants have not answered.

Summary of 2023 responses: When aggregating the responses corresponding to ‘very important’ and ‘important,’ the survey respondents identified Open Access, ORCID, and open data/data sharing as the top three practices they considered crucial for their career development.

	Very important		Important		Neutral		Unimportant		Very unimportant	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Open Access	94	49.5	51	26.8	29	15.3	11	5.8	5	2.6
Open Data	63	33.7	56	29.9	46	24.6	17	9.1	5	2.7
Open Software/Code	48	26.7	47	26.1	45	25.0	24	13.3	16	8.9
Study Preregistration	52	31.9	35	21.5	29	17.8	27	16.6	20	12.3
Preprint Archiving	57	33.3	50	29.2	27	15.8	22	12.9	15	8.8
Open Monographs	55	36.9	28	18.8	22	14.8	22	14.8	22	14.8
Open Licences	52	30.1	49	28.3	42	24.3	18	10.4	12	6.9
ORCID Identifier	74	41.3	56	31.3	33	18.4	10	5.6	6	3.4
Open Edu. Resources	66	37.9	42	24.1	42	24.1	13	7.5	11	6.3

2020 vs 2023: In the 2020 survey, participants were asked the same question (Q4). The table below shows a comparison of 2020 versus 2023 based on ‘very important’ and ‘important’ responses. In the 2023 survey, respondents consistently rated all open practices as more important or very important for their career than in the 2020 survey. Open monographs, preregistration, and ORCID were the three practices with the greatest increase in ratings compared to 2020.

	2020	2023	diff
Open Access	72.6	76.3	3.7
Open Data	61.8	63.6	1.8
Open Software/Code	49.7	52.8	3.1
Study Preregistration	22.5	53.4	30.9
Preprint Archiving	38.2	62.5	24.3
Open Monographs	24.5	55.7	31.2
Open Licences	40.6	58.4	17.8
ORCID Identifier	46.9	72.6	25.7
Open Edu. Resources	0	62	NA

Q10: Do you work with data?

This question was included in the survey to check respondents’ understanding of the term ‘data’ (i.e., that it includes a wide range of materials in digital and non-digital formats). The results of this question are used to compare to responses to Q12 “What types of information do you typically collect, observe, generate or create as part of your research?” Almost all respondents (86.5%) reported that they work with data.

	n	%
Yes	173	86.5
No	16	8.0
I don't conduct research	9	4.5
Other (please specify)	2	1.0
Total	200	100.0

n = 162 participants have not answered.

Other	n
Only with very small amounts of data, nearly always reported in the paper in question.	1
Sometimes	1

Q11: Have you ever applied for funding within a research grant application to support open data/data sharing practices (e.g., research time for preparing data for sharing, data storage costs etc.)?

Just over a quarter of respondents do not know whether it is possible to apply for funding to support open data/data sharing from their funders (28.7%). A quarter of participants are already applying for such funding (25.9%), and 21.3% plan to.

	n	%
No, I don't know if this is possible with my funders	50	28.7
Yes	45	25.9
No, but I plan to	37	21.3
Other (please specify)	16	9.2
No, because these are not substantial data sharing costs in my research	13	7.5
No, because I don't share my data	10	5.7
No, I know that my funders don't allow this	3	1.7
Total	174	100.0

n = 188 participants have not answered.

Other	n
I don't apply for funding	6
?	1
hasn't come up yet but keeping it in mind	1
I am taking this time into account, but it is not set aside within grants systems, and therefore "invisible", while it takes months for big datasets	1
I haven't seen any funding for this, so No	1
Just haven't thought to do this before and usually trying to reduce costs	1

Other	n
No	1
no as data is provided as a figure in the paper	1
no, haven't thought about doing it	1
No. The data I collect is made freely available on Uni databases, or is summarised in entirety in publications (in supplementary materials).	1
Not yet been an issue	1

(Note for future surveys: "Other" was well used as a response. Based on the "other" responses amend the options for this question to better capture potential responses.)

Responses from Mid & Established Researchers: When considering responses from only mid/recognised and established/experienced researchers, the percentage of respondents who did not know it was possible to apply funding to support data sharing remains just over a quarter (26%). However, a larger proportion of respondents reported already applying for such funding (38.4%).

	n	%
Yes	28	38.4
No, I don't know if this is possible with my funders	19	26.0
No, but I plan to	8	11.0
No, because these are not substantial data sharing costs in my research	7	9.6
Other (please specify)	6	8.2
No, because I don't share my data	3	4.1
No, I know that my funders don't allow this	2	2.7
Total	73	100.0

Q12: What types of information do you typically collect, observe, generate or create as part of your research? Please tick all that apply.

Respondents reported working with a wide range of data sources, with quantitative information (56.3%), text documents and/or spreadsheets (56.3%), and questionnaires and/or codebooks (42.1%) being the three most commonly cited.

	n	% of respondents
Quantitative information	111	56.3
Text documents and/or spreadsheets	111	56.3
Questionnaires and/or codebooks	83	42.1
Protocols and/or methodologies	77	39.1
Code	72	36.5
Images and/or photographs	70	35.5
Interview schedules and/or transcripts	59	29.9

	n	% of respondents
Audio	55	27.9
Lab notebooks	55	27.9
Specimens and/or samples	44	22.3
Video	42	21.3
Archival documents and/or historical artefacts	21	10.7
Collections of digital objects	19	9.6
Other (please specify)	7	3.6
I don't conduct research	6	3.0

n = 197 participants have answered.

n = 165 participants have not answered.

Note: Due to there being multiple response options per participant, percentages are calculated based on the number of participants rather than the number of responses.

Other	n
Books and papers	1
Clinical	1
Formatted datasets	1
Measurement of data from radio	1
Performances and artworks	1
Scientific hypotheses and theories; also, the results of numerical simulations	1
Very large data files	1

The purpose of including Q10 (Do you work with data?) and Q12 in the survey was to assess respondents' comprehension of the term 'data'. All items listed in Q12 are categorised as data. Therefore, if participants indicated in Q10 that they do not work with data but selected any category in Q12, it suggests a potential misunderstanding of the term 'data'. Consequently, these respondents may not realise that data policies are applicable to their work. In Q10, 16 (8%) respondents indicated that they do not work with data, but based on their responses to Q12, all are working with data (defined as information they typically collect, observe, generate or create as part of their research). They reported working with the following information (data):

	n
Questionnaires and/or codebooks	6
Text documents and/or spreadsheets	5
Audio	4
Images and/or photographs	4
Video	4
Other (please specify)	3

	n
Quantitative information	3
Archival documents and/or historical artefacts	2
Code	2
Interview schedules and/or transcripts	2
Protocols and/or methodologies	2
Collections of digital objects	1
I don't conduct research	1

n = 162 participants have not answered.

Other	n
Books and papers	1
Measurement of data from radio	1
Performances and artworks	1

Q13: With reference to open data/data sharing, what problems or concerns (if any) do you have with sharing data? Select up to 3.

Respondents were asked to select up to three responses: n = 44 selected one, n = 31 selected two, and n = 116 selected three.

The biggest concern about open data/data sharing was that data contain sensitive and/or personal information (44%), followed by organising data in a presentable and useful way (26.2%), and not knowing what repository to use (21.5%), and being unsure about copyright and licensing (21.5%). The least frequently cited concerns were data are too small or unimportant (3.7%), I have no desire to share my data (3.1%), others may not be able to repeat my findings (3.1%).

	n	% of respondents
Data contain sensitive and/or personal information	84	44.0
Organising data in a presentable and useful way	50	26.2
I do not know what repository to use	41	21.5
Unsure about copyright and licensing	41	21.5
Unsure I have the rights to share	37	19.4
Data are too large to share	36	18.8
Concerns about misuse of data	34	17.8
Not receiving appropriate credit or acknowledgement	33	17.3
I have no problems/concerns about sharing data	24	12.6
I do not know how to share data	19	9.9
I do not perceive data sharing as a core element of my job	11	5.8
Others may find errors in my data	10	5.2

	n	% of respondents
Another lab may make a different interpretation of my data	8	4.2
Data are too small or unimportant	7	3.7
Other (please specify)	7	3.7
I have no desire to share my data	6	3.1
Others may not be able to repeat my findings	6	3.1

n = 191 participants have answered.

n = 171 participants have not answered.

Note: Due to there being multiple response options per participant, percentages are calculated based on the number of participants rather than the number of responses.

Other	n
Additional time required	5
I may still plan on working with the data and do not see why I should share data not fully exploited	1
Surrey has had several different “big data” storage deals since I’ve been here (only a few years!) and when they change every year, with zero support from management (senior or local), it’s VERY frustrating.	1

2020 vs 2023: In the 2020 survey, participants were presented with the same question (Q9), and were allowed to select all applicable options. In the 2023 survey, participants were instructed to choose up to three options. Consequently, we focus on comparing the relative rankings rather than changes in the percentage of respondents citing each barrier.

In both surveys, two consistent concerns appeared among the top three: data contain sensitive and/or personal information, and unsure about copyright and licensing. In 2023, organising data in a presentable and useful way, and I do not know what repository to use (jointly ranked third with copyright and licensing), were also ranked in the top three. In contrast, in 2020, unsure I have the rights to share, occupied the third position.

	2020 %	2023 %
Data contain sensitive and/or personal information	46.6	44.0
Organising data in a presentable and useful way	33.4	26.2
I do not know what repository to use	37.3	21.5
Unsure about copyright and licensing	51.0	21.5
Unsure I have the rights to share	38.8	19.4
Data are too large to share	21.0	18.8
Concerns about misuse of data	41.0	17.8
Not receiving appropriate credit or acknowledgement	38.8	17.3
I have no problems/concerns about sharing data	14.1	12.6

	2020 %	2023 %
I do not know how to share data	NA	9.9
I do not perceive data sharing as a core element of my job	NA	5.8
Others may find errors in my data	9.5	5.2
Another lab may make a different interpretation of my data	11.5	4.2
Data are too small or unimportant	16.1	3.7
Other (please specify)	9.0	3.7
I have no desire to share my data	4.9	3.1
Others may not be able to repeat my findings	7.1	3.1

Q14: With reference to open data/data sharing, what do you consider the incentives are (if any) for sharing your data? Select up to 3.

Respondents were asked to select up to three responses: n = 20 selected one, n = 22 selected two, n = 117 selected three, and n = 32 selected four.

When considering the incentives for sharing data, 50.8% of respondents cited public benefit, followed by increased impact and visibility of my research (47.6%), and transparency (37.2%). The least frequently cited incentives were I don't perceive any incentives to sharing my data (7.3%), my data can be used in teaching (4.7%), and my data will have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) (3.1%).

	n	% of respondents
Public benefit	97	50.8
Increased impact and visibility of my research	91	47.6
Transparency	71	37.2
Increased opportunities for collaboration	59	30.9
Others can re-use and build on my data	43	22.5
Increase the ability of editors	38	19.9
reviewers and researchers to understand my research	38	19.9
My research will receive a higher level of citations	30	15.7
It will incentivise me to make sure that my data are as robust and reproducible as possible	29	15.2
I will get credit for sharing data	16	8.4
I don't perceive any incentives to sharing my data	14	7.3
My data can be used in teaching	9	4.7
My data will have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	6	3.1
Other (please specify)	2	1.0

n = 191 participants have answered.

n = 171 participants have not answered.

Note: Due to there being multiple response options per participant, percentages are calculated based on the number of participants rather than the number of responses.

Other	n
I don't use statistical data	1
My institution wants me to do this but I don't know how.	1

2020 vs 2023: In the 2020 survey, participants were presented with the same question (Q10), and were allowed to select all applicable options. In the 2023 survey, participants were instructed to choose up to three options. Consequently, we focus on comparing the relative rankings rather than changes in the percentage of respondents citing each barrier.

In both surveys, two consistent incentives appeared among the top three: Public benefit, and increased impact and visibility of my research. In 2023, transparency was also ranked in the top three. In contrast, in 2020, increased opportunities for collaboration, occupied the third position. Note that in the 2020 survey, transparency and reuse were combined, but in the 2023 survey they were offered as separate options.

	2020	2023
	%	%
Public benefit	62.4	50.8
Increased impact and visibility of my research	65.4	47.6
Transparency	52.4	37.2
Increased opportunities for collaboration	59.6	30.9
Others can re-use and build on my data	52.4	22.5
Increase the ability of editors	NA	19.9
reviewers and researchers to understand my research	NA	19.9
My research will receive a higher level of citations	37.3	15.7
It will incentivise me to make sure that my data are as robust and reproducible as possible	40.5	15.2
I will get credit for sharing data	28.3	8.4
I don't perceive any incentives to sharing my data	NA	7.3
My data can be used in teaching	NA	4.7
My data will have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	19.0	3.1
Other (please specify)	5.6	1.0

Q15: Where do you get the majority of your information, training, and guidance on Open Research practices?

Just under half of respondents (45.7%) reported using internal University of Surrey sources as their main reference for information, training, and guidance on Open Research practices, 32.4% reported using a mix of Surrey and non-Surrey sources, and 21.8% mainly relied on non-Surrey sources.

	n	%
Internal Surrey sources	86	45.7
About an equal mix of Surrey and non-Surrey sources	61	32.4
Non-Surrey sources	41	21.8
Total	188	100.0

n = 174 participants have not answered.

Other	n
did not really have any training	1
I'm just a technician. Nobody knows me	1
Just Google it	1
Self taught	1
too early in project	1
Too new in academia (only started 2 weeks ago).	1

By faculty

	Junior		Early		Recognised		Established	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Internal Surrey sources	19	36.5	29	48.3	26	55.3	12	41.4
About an equal mix of Surrey and non-Surrey sources	22	42.3	15	25.0	12	25.5	12	41.4
Non-Surrey sources	11	21.2	16	26.7	9	19.1	5	17.2
Total	52	100.0	60	100.0	47	100.0	29	100.0

Q16: Specifically from where do you usually receive information, training, and guidance on Open Research practices? Please tick all that apply.

The Open Research webpages (40.0%), Open Research training module (31.8%), and supervisor, line manager or Surrey peer or colleague (27.2%) were the three most frequently cited specific sources of information.

	n	% of respondents
Surrey Open Research webpages	78	40.0
Surrey Open Research training module	62	31.8
Supervisor / Line manager / Surrey peer or colleague	53	27.2
Literature	48	24.6
Surrey Open Research Team at the library	48	24.6
Other Surrey training / workshops / conferences	42	21.5
Non-Surrey peer or colleague / Networking at conferences	30	15.4
I don't seek guidance on Open Research practices	29	14.9
Social media	27	13.8
Common practice in the department or lab	26	13.3
Publisher	26	13.3
External training / workshops / conferences	24	12.3
Funder	21	10.8
Mailing list / Forum / Wiki	16	8.2
My Faculty Engagement Librarian (FEL)	12	6.2
Professional Society	12	6.2
Other (please specify)	8	4.1
Surrey innovation / Legal team (re IP)	5	2.6

n = 195 participants have answered.

n = 167 participants have not answered.

Other	n
Asking Qs by email	1
Google	1
junk emails	1
Surrey Reproducibility Society	1
Too new.	1
Youtube, Blogs, Github	1

2020 vs 2023: In the 2020 survey, participants were asked the same question (Q11). In the 2023 survey, options were added (e.g., Open Research webpages and module) and some were removed (see below note). Consequently, we focus on comparing the relative rankings rather than changes in the percentage of respondents citing each source of information.

In the 2023 survey, the Open Research webpages (40.0%), Open Research training module (31.8%), and supervisor, line manager or Surrey peer or colleague (27.2%) were the three most frequently cited specific sources of information. The Open Research webpages and the module were not

included as options in the 2020 survey; however, they emerged as essential initiatives resulting from the survey. In contrast, in 2020, the three most frequently mentioned sources of information were literature (38.1%), non-Surrey peer or colleague/networking at conferences (37.6%), and common practice in the department or lab (26.3%).

	2020 %	2023 %
Surrey Open Research webpages	NA	40.0
Surrey Open Research training module	NA	31.8
Supervisor / Line manager / Surrey peer or colleague	22.9	27.2
Literature	38.1	24.6
Surrey Open Research Team at the library	17.7	24.6
Other Surrey training / workshops / conferences	8.6	21.5
Non-Surrey peer or colleague / Networking at conferences	37.6	15.4
I don't seek guidance on Open Research practices	NA	14.9
Social media	18.4	13.8
Common practice in the department or lab	26.3	13.3
Publisher	18.4	13.3
External training / workshops / conferences	NA	12.3
Funder	9.6	10.8
Mailing list / Forum / Wiki	10.8	8.2
My Faculty Engagement Librarian (FEL)	4.2	6.2
Professional Society	11.1	6.2
Other (please specify)	14.3	4.1
Surrey innovation / Legal team (re IP)	NA	2.6

Note: In the 2020 survey, 'Supervisor' (22.9%) was a standalone option, where in 2023 it was combined into 'Supervisor / Line manager / Surrey peer or colleague'. 'Surrey Reproducibility Society' (5.9%) was removed because it was inactive. 'Local 'methods person' / statistician / data analyst' (3.9%) was also removed.

Q17: Do you have the autonomy to make decisions about where to publish your research work?

	n	%
Yes	141	72.3
No	29	14.9
I don't (currently) publish	25	12.8
Total	195	100.0

n = 167 participants have not answered.

Q18: When working on a new research project, what factors play a role in your choice of journal for publication? Drag and drop the answers to rank them in order of importance.

Respondents ranked journal aims and scope make it a good fit for my topic, journal impact factor (JIF), and research rigour as the three most important factors when choosing a journal to publish in.

	Overall rank
Journal aims and scope make it a good fit for my topic	1
Journal impact factor (JIF)	2
Research rigour	3
Peer review and editorial quality	4
Speed of review and/or publication	5
Broad readership	6
Journal accepts Registered Reports	7
Other (please specify)	8

Other	n
Open access	4
Publication costs	2
Only 1 to 3 - 1	1
It's where my subject area publishes; (2) Status of journal	1
There is an expectation from my professional registration body that we publish in the college owned journal	1
Status of the publication	1
Journal reputation/prestige in the field	1
Journals I am familiar with	1
Too new to make this judgement yet	1
Academic Journal Guide (former ABS list) journal	1

Q19: Within the research environment, how relevant is the responsible use of metrics to you personally (i.e., the responsible use of quantitative indicators of research activity, such as publication metrics)? Please select all that apply.

When asked about responsible metrics, 41.5% of respondents reported being unfamiliar with the term. Around a quarter (23.1%) felt that such metrics were relevant, and generally practised responsibly, and 20% that they were relevant but not always practised responsibly.

	n	% of respondents
I am unfamiliar with the term responsible use of metrics	81	41.5
Metrics are relevant to my work and in my experience are generally practised responsibly	45	23.1

	n	% of respondents
Metrics are relevant to my work but in my experience are not always practised responsibly	39	20.0
I don't consider research metrics relevant to my work / field	29	14.9
I actively adhere to a responsible metrics framework	24	12.3
I have encountered research metrics used in an irresponsible way	23	11.8

n = 195 participants have answered.

n = 167 participants have not answered.

Q20: Are you clear about what Open Research practices you should be engaging in in order to meet University policy?

Just under half of respondents (46.7%) reported being clear or very clear about the Open Research practices they should be engaging in in order to meet University policy, 27.2% were unclear or very unclear, and 26.2% were neither clear nor unclear.

	n	%
Clear	75	38.5
Neither clear nor unclear	51	26.2
Unclear	43	22.1
Very clear	16	8.2
Very unclear	10	5.1
Total	195	100.0

n = 167 participants have not answered.

Q21: Reflecting on the past three years, do you think that the Open Research culture at the University has changed?

Just under half of respondents (46.2%) felt that over the last three years there is more of an Open Research culture at the University, 5% felt the culture had not changed, and just 2% felt that there was less of an Open Research culture. The remaining 46% did not know (23.6%) or had not been at the University for three years (22.6%).

Among respondents who had been at the University for the past three years (i.e., excluding the 22.6% who had not been), almost two-thirds (59.6%) felt that the Open Research culture had improved.

	n	%
Yes, there is more of an Open Research culture	90	46.2
Don't know	46	23.6
Not applicable, I haven't been at the University for three years	44	22.6

	n	%
No, it hasn't changed	10	5.1
Yes, there is less of an Open Research culture	4	2.1
Other (please specify)	1	0.5
Total	195	100.0

n = 167 participants have not answered.

The respondent that selected 'Other' did not provide any additional text.

Q22: As an institution, what one practical thing could we do to promote an Open Research culture?

In terms of the one thing that the University could do to promote an Open Research culture, six key themes arose:

1. To (concisely) communicate which open practices are necessary/ how Open Research applies to researchers
2. Increase the availability of funding. This was most often mentioned in respect to covering Open Access publishing and open monograph costs
3. Provide the time necessary to both learn about and practice Open Research
4. Provide recognition and reward to incentivise Open Research practices
5. Offer more resources, training, and how to guides
6. Provide faculty-level support

This question was answered by 81 respondents. See Appendix C for full responses.

Q23: Do you have any other comments?

Responses to the comments questions were predominantly idiosyncratic, but three themes emerged:

1. Open Research takes time and effort, and we should aim to integrate Open Research into existing processes
2. The survey was too long/poorly designed. All but one of these comments come from respondents to the full UKRN survey
3. Funding is required to support Open Access publishing. One respondent noted the large profits publishers are making.

This question was answered by 89 respondents. See Appendix D for full responses.

UKRN Questions

This evaluation reports a subset of the UKRN questions. A full analysis of all questions, conducted by the team leading the UKRN survey at the University of Manchester, is provided in Appendix F. Note that the UKRN analysis did not exclude one participant who reported not working in research, where this report does. A sample size of n = 213 started answering the UKRN questions.

A summary of responses to Q1.1 to Q14.1 is presented in Appendix E.

1. Research Co-production

Q1.1: Research co-production is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	62	34.6
Medium	51	28.5
Low	34	19.0
I am not aware of this	32	17.9
Total	179	100.0

n = 34 participants have not answered.

Q1.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 27.4% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 42.5%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 30.2%).

n = 34 participants have not answered.

Q1.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	134	74.9
Yes	40	22.3
Yes, but not found	5	2.8
Total	179	100.0

n = 34 participants have not answered.

Q1.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 40 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	17	50.0
At the right level	8	23.5
Available	8	23.5
I do not know	3	8.8
Too basic	3	8.8
Hard to access	2	5.9

	n	% of respondents
Other. Please explain:	2	5.9
Non-existent	1	2.9

n = 34 participants have answered.

n = 6 participants (out of the 40 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
Some available, certainly not non-existent, but not plentiful either. I and others have had to go outside the institution to develop skills in codesign and coproduction for example, with the point of care, Foundation	1
There is no formal training as such on co-production at my institution but I have colleagues with expertise in this and they have shared it with me and coached me.	1

Q1.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	98	64.1
Monitoring and compliance	24	15.7
Passive	17	11.1
Recognition and reward	14	9.2
Total	153	100.0

n = 60 participants have not answered.

Q1.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	103	67.3
Ok	30	19.6
Very well	13	8.5
Not very well	7	4.6
Total	153	100.0

n = 60 participants have not answered.

2. OR Legal and Ethical

Q2.1: Conducting open research consistent with relevant legal, ethical, and regulatory constraints is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	100	69.9
Medium	25	17.5
Low	11	7.7
I am not aware of this	7	4.9
Total	143	100.0

n = 70 participants have not answered.

Q2.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 11.9% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 30.8%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 57.3%).

n = 70 participants have not answered.

Q2.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	74	51.7
Yes	65	45.5
Yes, but not found	4	2.8
Total	143	100.0

n = 70 participants have not answered.

Q2.7 The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 65 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	38	59.4
Available	25	39.1
At the right level	20	31.2
Too basic	5	7.8
Hard to access	3	4.7
I do not know	3	4.7
Other. Please explain:	2	3.1

n = 64 participants have answered.

n = 1 participants (out of the 65 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
Emphasises over-compliance rather than sensible and practical approaches	1
I have had both positive and negative experiences with ethics training. My colleagues have been very supportive in this topic.	1

Q2.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
Monitoring and compliance	60	45.5
I do not know	40	30.3
Passive	16	12.1
Recognition and reward	16	12.1
Total	132	100.0

n = 81 participants have not answered.

Q2.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	56	42.4
Ok	48	36.4

	n	%
Very well	19	14.4
Not very well	9	6.8
Total	132	100.0

n = 81 participants have not answered.

3. Transparent Qualitative Data Practices

Q3.1: Transparent qualitative data practices are something I think have a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	54	43.9
Medium	29	23.6
Low	25	20.3
I am not aware of this	15	12.2
Total	123	100.0

n = 90 participants have not answered.

Q3.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 30.1% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 25.2%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 44.7%).

n = 90 participants have not answered.

Q3.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	95	77.2
Yes	21	17.1
Yes, but not found	7	5.7
Total	123	100.0

n = 90 participants have not answered.

Q3.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 21 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	16	76.2
At the right level	8	38.1
Available	5	23.8
Too basic	3	14.3
Hard to access	1	4.8
I do not know	1	4.8

	n	% of respondents
Other. Please explain:	1	4.8

n = 21 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 21 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
This will probably depend on the discipline and supervisors/lecturers, etc.	1

Q3.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	70	57.9
Monitoring and compliance	24	19.8
Passive	19	15.7
Recognition and reward	8	6.6
Total	121	100.0

n = 92 participants have not answered.

Q3.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	72	59.5
Ok	25	20.7
Very well	16	13.2
Not very well	8	6.6
Total	121	100.0

n = 92 participants have not answered.

4. Defining the Data, Code, or Other Evidence

Q4.1: Defining the data, code, or other evidence on which your research findings will be based on and how this will be managed and shared before the start of data collection and analysis (e.g., Data Management Plans) is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	65	56.5
Medium	32	27.8

	n	%
Low	14	12.2
I am not aware of this	4	3.5
Total	115	100.0

n = 98 participants have not answered.

Q4.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 10.4% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 24.3%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 65.2%).

n = 98 participants have not answered.

Q4.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	65	56.5
Yes	42	36.5
Yes, but not found	8	7.0
Total	115	100.0

n = 98 participants have not answered.

Q4.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 42 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	18	43.9
At the right level	14	34.1
Available	12	29.3
Too basic	5	12.2
Other. Please explain:	3	7.3
I do not know	2	4.9
Hard to access	1	2.4

n = 41 participants have answered.

n = 1 participants (out of the 42 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
I have experienced mixed advice on this topic that has not been consistent.	1
Poor, too generic	1
There is a paradox as the typical academic response is both: "don't tell me how to record my research" and "just tell me exactly what you want us to do."	1

Q4.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	48	42.9
Monitoring and compliance	38	33.9
Passive	19	17.0
Recognition and reward	7	6.2
Total	112	100.0

n = 101 participants have not answered.

Q4.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	52	46.4
Ok	35	31.2
Very well	13	11.6

	n	%
Not very well	12	10.7
Total	112	100.0

n = 101 participants have not answered.

5. Pre-registration

Q5.1: Pre-registration of research protocols (may include registered reports) is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
Low	38	34.5
High	31	28.2
Medium	22	20.0
I am not aware of this	19	17.3
Total	110	100.0

n = 103 participants have not answered.

Q5.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 43.6% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 31.8%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 24.5%).

n = 103 participants have not answered.

Q5.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	98	89.1
Yes	11	10.0
Yes, but not found	1	0.9
Total	110	100.0

n = 103 participants have not answered.

Q5.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 11 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	6	54.5
At the right level	5	45.5
Available	3	27.3
Hard to access	1	9.1
I do not know	1	9.1
Too basic	1	9.1

n = 11 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 11 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q5.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	67	62.0
Monitoring and compliance	19	17.6
Passive	14	13.0
Recognition and reward	8	7.4
Total	108	100.0

n = 105 participants have not answered.

Q5.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	71	65.7
Ok	20	18.5
Very well	10	9.3
Not very well	7	6.5
Total	108	100.0

n = 105 participants have not answered.

6. Open Source Software created by others

Q6.1: Using open source software created by others is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	39	36.4
Medium	33	30.8
Low	21	19.6
I am not aware of this	14	13.1
Total	107	100.0

n = 106 participants have not answered.

Q6.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 27.1% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 31.8%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 41.1%).

n = 106 participants have not answered.

Q6.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	89	83.2
Yes	12	11.2
Yes, but not found	6	5.6
Total	107	100.0

n = 106 participants have not answered.

Q6.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 12 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Available	5	41.7
Good	5	41.7
I do not know	3	25.0

	n	% of respondents
Too basic	3	25.0
At the right level	2	16.7
Hard to access	1	8.3

n = 12 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 12 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q6.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	79	73.8
Monitoring and compliance	12	11.2
Passive	12	11.2
Recognition and reward	4	3.7
Total	107	100.0

n = 106 participants have not answered.

Q6.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	78	72.9
Ok	15	14.0
Not very well	10	9.3
Very well	4	3.7
Total	107	100.0

n = 106 participants have not answered.

7. Creating own Open Source Software

Q7.1: Creating my own open source software/analysis code to share with others is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
Low	41	39.8
Medium	29	28.2
High	17	16.5
I am not aware of this	16	15.5
Total	103	100.0

n = 110 participants have not answered.

Q7.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 50.5% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 30.1%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 19.4%).

n = 110 participants have not answered.

Q7.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	94	91.3
Yes	8	7.8
Yes, but not found	1	1.0
Total	103	100.0

n = 110 participants have not answered.

Q7.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 8 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	3	37.5
Too basic	3	37.5
At the right level	1	12.5
Available	1	12.5
Hard to access	1	12.5
I do not know	1	12.5

n = 8 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 8 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q7.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	73	71.6
Passive	16	15.7
Monitoring and compliance	8	7.8
Recognition and reward	5	4.9
Total	102	100.0

n = 111 participants have not answered.

Q7.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	77	75.5
Ok	17	16.7
Not very well	5	4.9
Very well	3	2.9
Total	102	100.0

n = 111 participants have not answered.

8. Version Control

Q8.1: Version control of research products (e.g., data, code, any other materials used in or generated as part of the research process) is something I think have a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	38	38.8

	n	%
Medium	22	22.4
I am not aware of this	21	21.4
Low	17	17.3
Total	98	100.0

n = 115 participants have not answered.

Q8.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 28.6% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 29.6%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 41.8%).

n = 115 participants have not answered.

Q8.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	86	87.8
Yes	12	12.2
Total	98	100.0

n = 115 participants have not answered.

Q8.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 12 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	5	41.7
Available	4	33.3
At the right level	3	25.0
I do not know	3	25.0
Hard to access	2	16.7
Non-existent	1	8.3
Other. Please explain:	1	8.3
Too basic	1	8.3

n = 12 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 12 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
some online documentation, quickly out of date	1

Q8.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	67	68.4
Monitoring and compliance	14	14.3
Passive	14	14.3
Recognition and reward	3	3.1
Total	98	100.0

n = 115 participants have not answered.

Q8.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	72	73.5
Ok	19	19.4
Not very well	4	4.1
Very well	3	3.1

	n	%
Total	98	100.0

n = 115 participants have not answered.

9. Own Data Analysis Computationally Reproducible

Q9.1: My own data analysis is computationally reproducible and this is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	42	43.3
Medium	22	22.7
Low	18	18.6
I am not aware of this	15	15.5
Total	97	100.0

n = 116 participants have not answered.

Q9.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 25.8% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 29.9%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 44.3%).

n = 116 participants have not answered.

Q9.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	84	86.6
Yes	8	8.2
Yes, but not found	5	5.2
Total	97	100.0

n = 116 participants have not answered.

Q9.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 8 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	5	62.5
Available	4	50.0
At the right level	3	37.5
Hard to access	1	12.5
I do not know	1	12.5

n = 8 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 8 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q9.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	69	71.1
Passive	15	15.5
Monitoring and compliance	9	9.3
Recognition and reward	4	4.1
Total	97	100.0

n = 116 participants have not answered.

Q9.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	66	68.0
Ok	18	18.6
Not very well	8	8.2
Very well	5	5.2
Total	97	100.0

n = 116 participants have not answered.

10. Preparing according to FAIR Principles

Q10.1: Preparing my own data, code, or other evidence according to FAIR principles is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	41	43.2
I am not aware of this	23	24.2
Medium	19	20.0
Low	12	12.6
Total	95	100.0

n = 118 participants have not answered.

Q10.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 31.6% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 24.2%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 44.2%).

n = 118 participants have not answered.

Q10.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	81	85.3
Yes	13	13.7
Yes, but not found	1	1.1
Total	95	100.0

n = 118 participants have not answered.

Q10.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 13 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	7	53.8
At the right level	5	38.5
Available	4	30.8
Too basic	2	15.4
I do not know	1	7.7
Other. Please explain:	1	7.7

n = 13 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 13 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
There is little appreciation that putting data into e.g. "OneNote" does not ensure ready access in 10 years time. Essentially zero awareness of meta data by most P.I.s, and still less interest.	1

Q10.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	65	68.4
Monitoring and compliance	12	12.6
Passive	11	11.6
Recognition and reward	7	7.4
Total	95	100.0

n = 118 participants have not answered.

Q10.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	67	70.5
Ok	19	20.0
Very well	6	6.3
Not very well	3	3.2
Total	95	100.0

n = 118 participants have not answered.

11. Guidelines for Recognising Contributions

Q11.1 Guidelines for recognising the specific substantive contribution of everyone involved in a research project is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	46	49.5
Medium	28	30.1
Low	12	12.9
I am not aware of this	7	7.5
Total	93	100.0

n = 120 participants have not answered.

Q11.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 12.9% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 30.1%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 57%).

n = 120 participants have not answered.

Q11.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	86	92.5
Yes	4	4.3
Yes, but not found	3	3.2
Total	93	100.0

n = 120 participants have not answered.

Q11.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 4 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	3	75
At the right level	1	25
Available	1	25

n = 4 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 4 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q11.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	55	59.1
Passive	20	21.5
Monitoring and compliance	12	12.9
Recognition and reward	6	6.5
Total	93	100.0

n = 120 participants have not answered.

Q11.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	60	64.5
Ok	17	18.3
Not very well	9	9.7
Very well	7	7.5
Total	93	100.0

n = 120 participants have not answered.

12. Declaring Conflicts of Interest

Q12.1: Declaring conflicts of interest is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	62	67.4
Medium	19	20.7
Low	9	9.8
I am not aware of this	2	2.2
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q12.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 8.7% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 19.6%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 71.7%).

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q12.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	86	93.5
Yes	5	5.4
Yes, but not found	1	1.1
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q12.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 5 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	3	60
At the right level	2	40
Available	2	40

n = 5 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 5 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q12.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	54	58.7
Monitoring and compliance	18	19.6
Passive	17	18.5
Recognition and reward	3	3.3
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q12.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	59	64.1
Ok	21	22.8
Very well	7	7.6
Not very well	5	5.4
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

13. Pre-prints

Q13.1: Publishing pre-prints is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
Medium	36	39.1
High	26	28.3
Low	21	22.8
I am not aware of this	9	9.8
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q13.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 32.6% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 32.6%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 34.8%).

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q13.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	83	90.2
Yes	7	7.6
Yes, but not found	2	2.2
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q13.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 7 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Available	5	71.4
At the right level	2	28.6
Good	2	28.6

n = 7 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 7 that saw the question) have not answered.

Q13.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
I do not know	63	68.5
Passive	16	17.4
Monitoring and compliance	7	7.6
Recognition and reward	6	6.5
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q13.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
I do not know	69	75.0
Ok	14	15.2
Very well	6	6.5
Not very well	3	3.3
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

14. Open Access (OA) Publications

Q14.1: Ensuring publications are Open Access (OA) is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research:

	n	%
High	72	78.3
Medium	18	19.6
Low	2	2.2
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q14.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):

Respondents were offered a slider to answer this question. 3.3% of respondents reported never having done this activity. We then grouped the remainder of the responses into those near to the 'never' end of the scale (i.e., scores of 1, 2, or 3; 17.4%), and those near to the 'very often' end (i.e., scores of 4, 5, or 6; 79.3%).

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q14.4 I have looked for training and support in this topic at my institution:

	n	%
No	56	60.9
Yes	36	39.1
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q14.7: The help at my institution on this topic is mainly [choose all that apply]:

This question was only displayed to the n = 36 respondents that answered 'yes' to having looked for training and support at their institution.

	n	% of respondents
Good	15	41.7

	n	% of respondents
Available	13	36.1
At the right level	10	27.8
Hard to access	4	11.1
I do not know	2	5.6
Other. Please explain:	2	5.6
Non-existent	1	2.8
Too basic	1	2.8

n = 36 participants have answered.

n = 0 participants (out of the 36 that saw the question) have not answered.

Other	n
slow and confusing	1
the problem is not the training, it is the money to cover OA	1

Q14.10: My institution takes mainly the following approach to this topic:

	n	%
Monitoring and compliance	36	39.1
I do not know	27	29.3
Recognition and reward	16	17.4
Passive	13	14.1
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Q14.11: And this approach (monitoring and compliance/recognition and reward/passive) works:

	n	%
Ok	33	35.9
I do not know	29	31.5
Very well	18	19.6
Not very well	12	13.0
Total	92	100.0

n = 121 participants have not answered.

Appendix A

Summary of responses to the Surrey question about awareness (Q7), and UKRN questions related to the awareness (Q1.1 – 14. 1) and practice (Q1.2 – 14.2) of various Open Research practices

Surrey description	UKRN description	Awareness (Q7) ^a		Awareness (Q7) ^a		Awareness (Q1.1-Q14.1) ^b		Practicing (Q1.2-Q14.2) ^c	
		All data		UKRN only		n	%	n	%
		n	%	n	%				
Open access	Open access	279	92.7	175	93.1	92	100	92	96.7
ORCID identifier	NA	244	81.1	164	87.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
Open data/sharing data	Own data analysis is computationally reproducible			142	75.5	82	84.5	72	74.2
	Preparing data, code, or other evidence according to FAIR	218	72.4	NA	NA	83	87.4	65	68.4
	Transparent qualitative data practices			NA	NA	108	87.8	86	69.9
Preprints	Preprints	198	65.8	141	75	83	90.2	62	67.4
Open software/code	Using open source software created by others	188	62.5	128	68.1	93	86.9	78	72.9
	Creating my own open source software/analysis code			NA	NA	87	84.5	51	48.0
Open licences	NA	181	60.1	119	63.3	NA	NA	NA	NA
Open edu. resources	NA	119	39.5	78	41.5	NA	NA	NA	NA
Study preregistration	Preregistration	115	38.2	76	40.4	91	82.7	62	56.4
Open monographs	NA	74	24.6	54	28.7	NA	NA	NA	NA
I'm not aware of any of these practices	NA	12	4	6	3.2	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	Research co-production	NA	NA	NA	NA	147	82.1	130	72.6
NA	Legal, ethical & regulatory constraints	NA	NA	NA	NA	136	95.1	126	88.1
NA	Defining the data, code, or other evidence (e.g., DMP)	NA	NA	NA	NA	111	96.5	103	89.6
NA	Version control	NA	NA	NA	NA	81	82.7	70	71.4
NA	Guidelines for recognising contributions	NA	NA	NA	NA	86	92.5	81	87.1
NA	Declaring conflicts of interest	NA	NA	NA	NA	90	97.8	84	91.3

Note. ^a Q7: Which of the following practices are you aware of? Hover over each item for more information (hovering only works on a computer). Please tick all that apply. ^b Q1.1 – 14.1: [Open Research practice e.g., 'Research co-production'] is something I think has a [low, medium, high] priority in my field of research. ^c Q1.2 – 14.2: I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often). The numbers reported here are the sum of 1-6 responses (i.e., all responses except 0 'never').

As noted in the Executive summary, we were not able to compare the percentage of respondents using various Open Research practices across the two surveys for several reasons: First, the questions are worded differently and offer different answer formats: In the 2020 survey, participants were asked to tick 'aware of', 'practicing myself' and/or 'accessing'. In the 2023 survey, participants were asked 'I do this type of activity in my field of research (0 - Never to 6 - Very often):' and used a slider to respond.

Second, the topics were described differently. For example, the 2020 survey asked about the practice of 'open software/code', whereas the 2023 survey asked separately about 'using open source software created by others' and 'creating my own open source software/analysis code to share with others'.

Third, as shown in the table above there is an inconsistency within the survey between responses to the Surrey question about awareness (Q7), and UKRN questions related to awareness (Q1.1 – 14. 1) and practice (Q1.2 – 14.2) of various Open Research practices. Three practices are directly comparable between the two sections of the survey: Open Access, preprints, and preregistration:

Awareness (Q7) vs Awareness (Q1.1 – 14. 1): For all three practices awareness is lower in Q7 than in Q1.1 – 14. 1: Open Access: 92.7% (Q7), 100% (Q1.1 – 14.1); preprints: 65.8% (Q7), 90.2% (Q1.1 – 14.1); preregistration: 38.2% (Q7), 82.7% (Q1.1 – 14.1).

Awareness (Q7) vs Practice (Q1.2 – 14.2): For the same three practices, the percentage of respondents that report using the practice (Q1.2 – 14.2) is higher than the percentage reporting being aware (Q7) of the practice: Open Access: 92.7% aware, 96.7% practicing; preprints: 65.8% aware, 67.4% practicing; preregistration: 38.2% aware, 56.4% practicing. Logically, it is not possible for more people to practice something than to be aware of it. Based on the 2020 survey and other previous research, we would expect the reverse to be true, and for an awareness-behaviour gap to be present. Furthermore, 69.9% of respondents reported using 'transparent qualitative data practices' despite only 56.5% reporting to use mixed or qualitative methods in their research (Q1).

One possible explanation for the inconsistency is that the Surrey and UKRN questions are answered by different cohorts, with the Surrey question being answered by a larger sample. However, even when the cohorts are directly comparable (i.e., when analysing only responses to the full survey) the disparity is still present (see table above). A more likely explanation is in the syntactical differences between the questions: The Surrey question asks directly about awareness, whereas the UKRN questions ask more indirectly. Q1.1 – 14. 1, asking about the extent to which the practice is a priority in the respondents' field of research has the option 'I am not aware of this'. The numbers reported above are the sum of 'low', 'medium', and 'high' responses (i.e., all responses other than 'I am not aware of this'). However, it is possible that respondents that were not aware of the practice reasoned that it must therefore be of low priority within their field of research, and selected 'low' rather than 'I am not aware of this'. Similarly, Q1.2 – 14.2 'I do this type of activity in my field of research' is more ambiguous and potentially open to misinterpretation than being asked to tick 'practicing myself'.

Appendix B

Career stage by Faculty

		n	%
FASS	Early	15	19.2
FASS	Established/Experienced	20	25.6
FASS	Junior	22	28.2
FASS	Mid/Recognised	16	20.5
FASS	NA	5	6.4
FEPS	Early	27	21.4
FEPS	Established/Experienced	11	8.7
FEPS	Junior	32	25.4
FEPS	Mid/Recognised	23	18.3
FEPS	NA	33	26.2
FHMS	Early	47	34.1
FHMS	Established/Experienced	14	10.1
FHMS	Junior	44	31.9
FHMS	Mid/Recognised	26	18.8
FHMS	NA	7	5.1
Other (please specify)	Early	1	9.1
Other (please specify)	Junior	4	36.4
Other (please specify)	Mid/Recognised	3	27.3
Other (please specify)	NA	3	27.3
Professional Services	Established/Experienced	1	33.3
Professional Services	NA	2	66.7
NA	NA	6	100.0

Appendix C

Responses to Q22: As an institution, what one practical thing could we do to promote an Open Research culture?

Key:

1. (Concisely) communicate what is necessary/ how OR applies to them
2. Increase funding – specifically to cover Open Access publishing costs
3. Barriers – time
4. Recognition & reward: incentivise/celebrate success/more support
5. More resources/training/how to
6. Faculty level

P1: Work out what is actually necessary to share

P2: Be more clear about how will support publishing costs.

P3: For established academics, lack of time is killer when combined with almost no incentives. Not sure OR people at Surrey can do much about that, sorry. Having said that sending round emails advertising two or three hour events may not be the best..

P4: Open-source my codes in Github if it's allowed

P5: tell me what you want me to do and how "open research" applies to me

P6: I don't see why a "culture" is needed: as with all things - they are my employer, so I will do as instructed regardless of what I may believe. All I need is a clear set of requirements and easily accessed instructions.

P7: Fund publishing OA for monographs

P8: Promote workshops/talks

P9: celebrate success

P10: provide resources

P11: More encouragement and support

P12: make it easy

P13: More training at different levels

P14: More information! Support that is specific to research topic

P15: Engage PhD students and better recognition

P16: Make the ethical review process more efficient

P17: Include in recognition and promotion practices

P18: Explain what you mean when you send emails about it - I thought it just meant open access before doing this survey!

P19: Have a quick checklist for different stages of the research process with general advice and examples, add it to the library website.

P20: have a dedicated data management per faculty to support the cleaning and storing of data sets

P21: Incentivise, probably

P22: Simplify open access availability

P23: Talk about it as though it were normal, typical, everyday practice and not something recent.

P24: Ensure all students and staff have an intro and/or complete a basic intro module (could be online/in person) on open research at an early stage in their learning or mandatory training.

P25: Mandate and incentivise reproducibility
 ## P26: Perhaps an experience sharing exercise university wide
 ## P27: I do not know
 ## P28: somewhere to save data
 ## P29: More training and incentives!
 ## P30: Demystify GDPR etc.
 ## P31: Explain what it is to new Year 1 researchers
 ## P32: resources, end focus on JIF.
 ## P33: Local faculty level communities of practice
 ## P34: all good
 ## P35: n/a
 ## P36: Include it in probation/appraisal/promotion targets
 ## P37: Raise awareness and provide necessary training to staff
 ## P38: Share best practices
 ## P39: Incentives and awards to motivate researchers.
 ## P40: Keep communicating/promoting it -
 ## P41: more case use examples
 ## P42: More info sessions
 ## P43: Assistance through qualified staff to help open research practices
 ## P44: Offer more training and workshops
 ## P45: Increase the funding.
 ## P46: Offer free online educational resources to spread awareness.
 ## P47: More Training
 ## P48: Time to complete training
 ## P49: Have a dedicated adviser within each department who is invested in the topic and whom other colleagues feel comfortable approaching. (Not sure if this is already done since my post is not academic)
 ## P50: A searchable database of research methods, codes, and data analysis pipelines - so the most appropriate collaborator or the person(s) with the required expertise for a certain project could be identified
 ## P51: Explain in concise and efficient way
 ## P52: Mentorship for early career researchers
 ## P53: Provide additional time in workload allocation models to practice good open research
 ## P54: More publicised funding availability
 ## P55: Improve
 ## P56: Facilitate grants for few months extension of research allocated to clean, improve and make code sharable.
 ## P57: Simple video training. I went to an event, it went on for hours. I was told how important OR is, and heard from people doing it. Not enough about what I should do and how - be succinct.
 ## P58: Personnel to prepare data for archiving
 ## P59: funding; clearer website
 ## P60: Improved methods for showing application of open research across departments, showing the incentive applications to this too (e.g. having an expert from an under-represented department showing how they have done it but also demonstrating the benefits they have seen for their career).
 ## P61: Audit (at ground level) What is the Data Management Plan for your research? How do you curate data? How do you identify samples? How do you share new processes with colleagues? Whose previous results are you building on - w

hat data was available?

P62: Mandatory training on Open Research

P63: Make Open Research Training a probation criterion for all staff with a research component.

P64: More active teaching of open research in masters courses

P65: Provide resources and funding to actively support it

P66: incentivise us to publish in top journals by guaranteeing to cover the costs of open access.

P67: provide training

P68: Rewards for open practice.

P69: Provide financial support for open access

P70: More training/information

P71: create incentives

P72: Continue to support early career academics in their engagement with O

A

P73: Clear leadership and direction

P74: open access for monographs

P75: Increase funding for open access licences (e.g. - purchase Oxford University Press subscription).

P76: I really hope that institute does this job by themselves

P77: funding

P78: More support to comply /. Time consuming

P79: Make the idea more visible within campus

P80: Training an career incentives

P81: I see the adverts, but nothing has changed in my daily research life.

Appendix D

Responses to Q23: Do you have any other comments?

Key:

1. Time and effort required
2. Survey was too long/poorly designed
3. Funding for OA publishing

Responses from respondents who completed the full UKRN survey:

```
## P1: .
## P2: None
## P3: Preparing data for a repository takes time and effort but like peer review, is important but UKRI etc just demand academics write down cookie-cutter data plans they then don't have time to implement. Until UKRI etc actually fund time and support, this will continue. Second point is that physics was doing pretty well using arXiv for green OA, then along came the government, Wellcome etc and the admin pain has just exploded. Please stop making OA harder.
## P4: No
## P5: N/A
## P6: survey was too long
## P7: no
## P8: Thi survey is poorly designed. Response "Never" (for the questions "How frequently...") is not accepted, questions are formally designed, it takes very long to fill it.
## P9: no
## P10: N/A
## P11: No
## P12: You could be more considerate of your respondents' time; more questions should be optional. Also, some people will have experience outside academia that is relevant.
## P13: I think the biggest obstacle to open research is when it's perceived to create more hoops for researchers to jump through - ideally we need processes that fit seamlessly into existing practices rather than created more work for everyone
## P14: Thought-provoking survey. Showed where my gaps are and also what extra training and supervision I might need to give to PGR students
## P15: No.
## P16: This survey took me longer than 20 minutes and I'm afraid I got fed-up with some of the questions - sorry!
## P17: No
## P18: No
## P19: no comments
## P20: fund open access publication for important papers
## P21: n/a
## P22: -
## P23: No
## P24: the costs and profits of scientific journal publishers at the expense of public funded institutions, i.e. staff, are abhorrent
```

P25: Maybe culture isn't the best word - more practice and practical
 ## P26: no
 ## P27: n/a
 ## P28: No other comments
 ## P29: No
 ## P30: No
 ## P31: no
 ## P32: NO
 ## P33: no
 ## P34: .
 ## P35: No, I do not have.
 ## P36: None
 ## P37: no
 ## P38: no
 ## P39: No
 ## P40: No
 ## P41: No
 ## P42: No
 ## P43: not applicable
 ## P44: Please adopt a more critical and less religious approach to open research
 ## P45: no - please let this questionnaire end soon
 ## P46: It's a culture shift
 ## P47: I do not have other comments
 ## P48: No
 ## P49: No further comments
 ## P50: No
 ## P51: no
 ## P52: no
 ## P53: No
 ## P54: no
 ## P55: No
 ## P56: funding for open access of monographs, please!
 ## P57: as an academic, I don't support this activity at all. This should be dealt in insitution and government levellevel
 ## P58: N/A

Responses from respondents who completed the condensed Surrey survey:

P1: No
 ## P2: no
 ## P3: No
 ## P4: No
 ## P5: no
 ## P6: non
 ## P7: no
 ## P8: For Open code sharing, the researcher with no good background in software design or writing codes have hesitations to make "codes" in a presentable manner. I suggest if this hesitation can be ignored or if we have

a open code publishing team like media team, thats gonna help the code to make publicly available.

P9: No

P10: None

P11: no

P12: no

P13: No

P14: Hope can have oppotunite to improve the english oral.

P15: The short informative session is useful. The one day workshop on open research is a waste of time

P16: no

P17: I personally was able to appreciate the support from Surrey for open access publishing - this was an encouranging experience. I am sure, these were well-spent money by the University.

P18: No

P19: No

P20: From my point of view, the transition to "Open Acces" is more or less complete, as far as formal publications are concerned. However, conference presentation and posters are another way of generating scientific impact and it is not clear to me that that the University has thought through the issue the issue how best to publicise these. [I normally mount most of my preprints on ArXiv and most of my presentations and posters on ResearchGate of makin

P21: No

P22: n/a

P23: N/A

P24: Researcher profiles, research facilitation, resources are not open/easy to find at Surrey's website. Generally, there is lack of digital resources, guidelines, and transparency.

P25: Such an important topic that I believe in passionately, but the incentives are really not there at the moment.

P26: no

P27: No

P28: biased survey - flawed likert structure - disappointing. will results be open access?

P29: No, I don't

P30: No

P31: Strange survey on a s

Appendix E

Summary of responses to UKRN questions Q1.1 to Q14.1; percentages ordered by frequency of 'High' responses.

	Open Access	Legal & ethics	Conflict of interest	DMPs	CRedit	Transparent qual data	Computational	FAIR data	Version control	Using open software	Co-production	Preprints	Prereg	Creating open software
High	78.3	69.9	67.4	56.5	49.5	43.9	43.3	43.2	38.8	36.4	34.6	28.3	28.2	16.5
Medium	19.6	17.5	20.7	27.8	30.1	23.6	22.7	20	22.4	30.8	28.5	39.1	20	28.2
Low	2.2	7.7	9.8	12.2	12.9	20.3	18.6	12.6	21.4	19.6	19	22.8	34.5	39.8
Not aware	0	4.9	2.2	3.5	7.5	12.2	15.5	24.2	17.3	13.1	17.9	9.8	17.3	16.5